

IMPACT OF NURSE LED CARDIAC REHABILITATION SESSION AMONG POST MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION CLIENTS

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Abstract

Background: The study aimed to assess the efficacy of cardiac nursing procedures namely cardiac rehabilitation, in improving the quality of life, medication adherence, and lifestyle modifications among post-myocardial infarction patients, in relation to their risk factors. **Methods:** This was quasi-experimental research that included 200 samples of post-myocardial infarction patients from a cardiology unit, chosen using a convenient sampling approach. The lifestyle modification assessment questionnaire was self-structured, and quantitative data was collected from the patients using the standardized WHO BREF scale and Morisky medication adherence scale. **Results:** After intervention, 53% of the experimental group had a moderate level of lifestyle modification score and none had a high level of lifestyle modification score, with 78.00% having a moderate level of quality-of-life score. After cardiac nurse interventions, 52% of Post MI patients exhibited good medication adherence. A significant positive correlation was found between quality of life and lifestyle modification ($r= 0.38, P=0.001^{***}$), as well as between lifestyle modification and medication adherence ($r= 0.34, P=0.001^{***}$). This suggests that as the score for lifestyle modification increases, so does the score for quality of life. Similarly, an increase in medication adherence score is associated with an increase in lifestyle modification score. **Conclusion:** By providing specific lifestyle modifications during the discharge process, the Cardiac Nursing intervention improved medication adherence and quality of life. The cardiac rehabilitation program deserves to be recognized to nurses working in cardiac wards.

Keywords: Cardiac Rehabilitation, Lifestyle Modification, Medication Adherence, Quality of Life.

INTRODUCTION

Myocardial Infarction can be "silent," go unnoticed, and a devastating incident that results in hemodynamic decline and early death.^[1] Cardiovascular diseases account for 32% of all deaths globally, with heart attacks and strokes contributing to 85% of these deaths.^[2]

The prevalence of cardiovascular disease (CVD) has consistently increased in most countries, particularly those that are not classified as high-income nations, during the previous few decades. India has one of the highest rates of cardiovascular disease (CVD) globally.^[3]

The frequency of coronary heart disease in India's population has fluctuated in recent decades, with rates ranging from 1.6% to 7.4% in rural regions and from 1% to 13.2% in metropolitan areas.^[4,5]

Lifestyle modifications can lower the chance of developing heart disease. It is possible to link poor lifestyle choices, such as smoking, eating poorly, and exercising insufficiently, to as many as half of all premature deaths.^[6] Because their hearts are in better form and don't have to work as hard, those who exercise frequently or who are exceptionally athletic usually have lower heart rates.^[7] Therapeutic interventions that focus on activities of daily living, physical functioning, and improving availability of mental healthcare may improve the health-related quality of life for individuals who have experienced a myocardial infarction.^[8] Patients diagnosed with post-acute coronary syndrome who have a diminished health-related quality of life (HRQoL) are at a higher risk of mortality, encountering severe cardiovascular events, and necessitating hospitalization.^[9]

Reducing cardiovascular risk to prevent recurrent cardiovascular events is difficult for people with CVD and their doctors. ^[10] In the field of medicine, secondary prevention is regarded as a critical issue that may be resolved by treating the primary risk factors, including obesity, diabetes, hypertension, and hypercholesteremia. Therefore, changing one's lifestyle also lowers cardiovascular morbidity and death, both singly and cumulatively.^[11]

One of the most successful methods for supporting secondary prevention in CVD patients is cardiac rehabilitation.^[12] The nurse-administered lifestyle modification intervention effectively improves lifestyle habits, including dietary choices, physical activity levels, medication adherence, and overall quality of life in patients recovering from myocardial infarction.^[13]

For a variety of reasons, post-MI patients' medication adherence was startlingly low. Increased adherence was only seen in early follow-up for younger age groups, addiction, and higher education levels.^[14,15]

Pharmacological illiteracy and forgetfulness were the leading causes of non-adherence.^[16] Patients educated according to the nursing care standard after suffering a myocardial infarction were more likely to adhere to their medication and lifestyle modifications.^[17,18]

Hence the researcher felt a need to investigate and intervene certain needs to enhance the life of post myocardial infarction patients. This study sought to evaluate the efficacy of cardiac nursing interventions that promote lifestyle modification and improving bio-physiological parameters in patients who have experienced a myocardial infarction.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research methodology used for this study was quasi-experimental. For data collection, 100 Post MI Patients in experimental and control group were deployed utilising convenient sampling Technique. The research was conducted in a tertiary hospital located in Chennai, namely in the cardiac department.

The study had specific conditions that needed to be fulfilled: a) Myocardial Infarction patients aged 30 years and above; b) Patients with hypertension and diabetes mellitus are included; c) Patients who can use android phone with internet; d) Patients with Myocardial Infarction who are on medical management without any complication; and e) Clinically stable with an ejection fraction of > 35%.

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

Data was collected from the participants after obtaining the proper permissions from the authorities of the institution. Permission from the ethics committee obtained vide ref no: EC/NEW/INST/2021/1618 prior the study process. The tool and the process of the study were validated by the experts of the fields of medicine, cardiology and nursing.

A Bio-socio demographic questionnaire, a self-structured lifestyle modification assessment questionnaire, a standardized WHO BREF scale, and a Morisky medication adherence scale were among the tools used to gather data. Approximately 15 minutes were spent on each participant to collect data using the chosen instrument. After collecting the pre-test, the cardiac nursing interventions were given to the Experimental group for a period of 20-30 minutes. The intervention group had been reinforced based on the interventions taught to them at first month and after three months the post-test had been conducted.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The experimental and control groups had 200 participants, with the age range of 41 to 50 years. Males make up a bigger proportion of both categories (86%&80%), and the skilled workers [43%&51%]. As demonstrated by the experimental group's pre-test, where no one had a low level of modification, 79% had a moderate level, and 21% had a high level, there was a significant difference in the Life Style Modification Assessment Scale scores between the experimental and control groups before and after the intervention. Post-test showed 47% of the experimental group had a low level of modification score, 53% had a moderate level of modification score, and none had a high level of modification score. [Figure1]

Figure 1: Comparison on Pretest and Post Test Percentage on Life Style Modification Scale Score Among Post MI Patients

There is a significant difference in life style assessment modification score between the experimental and control groups [$\chi^2=66.57$ $P=0.001^{***}(S)$]. It is congruent with the findings of a research conducted on 71 patients, which revealed that following cardiac rehabilitation in the Cardiac Rehabilitation group participated much more daily activity, social leisure, and physically demanding leisure activities than the non-cardiac rehabilitation control group. ($p < 0.001$).^[19]

The quality-of-life score differed considerably from the pre-test. Seventy-nine percent of the experimental group have a low QOL, thirty percent have a moderate QOL, and none have a high QOL. Sixty-eight percent of the control group have a low QOL, thirty-two percent have a moderate QOL, and none have a high QOL. However, following the cardiac nursing intervention, the experimental group's QOL score was found to be 8.00% poor, 78.00% moderate, and 14% good after the post-test. In contrast, the control group's QOL score was found to be 62.00% poor, 38.00% moderate, and none good before the intervention. ^[Figure 2]

Figure 2: Comparison on Pretest and Post Test Percentage on Quality-of-Life Score Among Post MI Patients

Moving forward, there is a significant difference in the quality of life between the experimental and control groups [$\chi^2=69.15$ $P=0.001^{***}(S)$]. The results corroborated with study conducted among 110 individuals concluding that there is a significant difference between two groups with and without cardiac rehabilitation. [17 ± 6.8 vs 22 ± 6.5 , $p<0.001$]^[20]

Medication adherence is critical after MI, and the individual score for medication adherence in the pre-test was in the experimental group, 70.00% of the patients have a low level of adherence, 22.00% had a moderate level of adherence, and 8% had a good level of adherence. In the control group, 66.00% of the patients had a low level of adherence, 25.00% had a moderate level of adherence, and 9% had a good level of adherence. Following intervention, 13.00% of patients in the experimental group had a low level of adherence, 52.00% had a moderate level of adherence, and 35% have a high level of adherence. Without intervention, individuals in the control group had a 1.41% lower medication adherence score. ^[Figure 3]

Figure 3 : Comparison on Pretest And Post Test Percentage On Medication Adherence Score Among Post MI Patients

There was an apparent difference between the experimental and control groups. [$\chi^2=53.10$ $P=0.001^{***}$ (S)]. The findings corroborate cohort research that found cardiac rehabilitation increased patients' adherence to medication and lifestyle improvements by reducing the barriers and improving their memory capacity.^[21]

Prior to intervention, there was no change in the bio physiological features of post-MI patients between the experimental and control groups. There exists a significant difference in SBP and DBP between the experimental and control groups after the nursing interventions.

The study variables in the experimental group and the control group showed a strong correlation. The QOL gain score and the adherence gain score have a substantial positive moderate correlation [$r= 0.44$ $P=0.001^{***}$]. The life style modification score and QOL gain score have a strong positive fair correlation. [$r= 0.38$ $P=0.001^{***}$]. The life style modification score and medication adherence score have a strong positive fair correlation. [$r= 0.34$ $P=0.001^{***}$].^[Table 1]

Table 1: Correlation Between Lifestyle Modification Scale Score, Quality of Life and Medication Adherence Among Post MI Patients In Experimental Group

	Correlation Between	Mean gain score Mean±SD	Karl pearson Correlation coefficients
Experimental group	QOL gain score Vs Adherence gain score	16.92±10.32 2.15±2.20	$r= 0.44$ $P=0.001^{***}$
	QOL gain score Vs Life style reduction gain score	16.92±10.32 17.63±5.43	$r= 0.38$ $P=0.001^{***}$
	Adherence gain score Vs Life style reduction gain score	2.15±2.20 17.63±5.43	$r= 0.34$ $P=0.001^{***}$

It aligned with research of 417 post-myocardial infarction patients that found a substantial correlation between patients' quality of life and their adherence to treatment regimens in order to improve their health.^[22]

CONCLUSION

The current study findings discovered that cardiac nurse interventions provided before to discharge improved the quality of life of the patients by encouraging medication adherence and lifestyle changes, as compared to the control group that received standard care. This emphasizes the significance of continuous support, education, counselling, and so on for those who are physically and mentally depressed as a result of a myocardial infarction. Nurse-led clinics assist patients enhance their lifestyle and extend their well-being, and policies may be developed to improve nurse-led clinics for post-MI patients

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Conflicts of Interest: No conflicts of interest.

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